

The Next Level Of Teeth Whitening - A Case Series

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Abstract

A pleasing appearance and bright smile greatly enhance one's personality. Discoloration, especially when the anterior teeth are affected, puts a significant disturbance of aesthetics and can decrease patient's self esteem. Public demand for esthetic dentistry, including tooth whitening especially anterior teeth has increased in recent years. Discoloration of a tooth is a common esthetic problem caused by either extrinsic or intrinsic factor. Now a days there are many advances for treating such teeth discolorations. The case report shows the remarkable change in the color of discolored teeth using in office bleaching.

Key words: In-office bleaching, vital bleaching, hydrogen peroxide, teeth whitening

Introduction

The lightening of the color of a tooth through the application of a chemical agent to oxidize the organic pigmentation in the tooth is referred to as tooth whitening¹. The normal color of permanent teeth is greyish yellow, greyish white, or yellowish white. Alterations or changes in the color may be physiologic or pathologic and endogenous or exogenous in nature¹. The Tooth discoloration is seen due to extrinsic or intrinsic stains. There are several methods available such as bleaching strips, bleaching pen, bleaching gel and laser bleaching¹. Teeth whitening has become the most requested procedure in dentistry today². There are two main types of bleaching procedures. Non-vital bleaching is done in a tooth which is root canal treated and has no nerve innervations. Vital bleaching is performed in a tooth which has live nerves³. The most common type of vital tooth whitening uses a gel-like whitening solution, applied directly on the tooth surface like hydrogen peroxide, sodium perborate, carbamide peroxide^{4,5}. Vital teeth bleaching is usually an in-office procedure and most popular system for in-office bleaching⁶. It uses a high concentration of hydrogen peroxide often referred to as "one-hour bleaching". These high concentrations of hydrogen peroxide range from 25%-40%⁷.

History

Firstly, Chloride and acetic acid were used as a bleaching agent in 1860 by Truman; he had used these agents for non-vital teeth. Then, Harlan (1884) used hydrogen peroxide for all discoloration for the first time. Haywood and Heymann (1989) proposed night guard vital bleaching for all stains. Garber and Goldstein(1991) suggested the combination of bleaching techniques (power & home).

Mechanism

The bleaching process is a result of oxidation and reduction reactions commonly known as 'Redox Reaction'. Free radicals with unpaired electrons are present in oxidizing agent, which it gives up. Thus become reduced (eg. hydrogen peroxide) whereas the tooth surface which is being bleached acts as reducing agent by accepting the electrons.

Case Report

Case 1: A 26 years old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics Chandra Dental College with the chief complaint of discoloration of teeth. During the oral examination of the patient, the key clinical guidelines that are focused on are no or minimal gingival recession, good periodontal health, and the absence of caries. In addition, questions about any history of tooth sensitivity were asked. The importance of this is that patients with a history of tooth sensitivity occasionally experience mild to moderate tooth sensitivity for 24 hours after in-office bleaching. In the case of this patient, he had no history of any tooth sensitivity.

Treatment Procedure

Figure 1: pre-operative Photograph

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The patient's initial shade was determined. It was A3. For this patient, Pola office plus from SDI was selected (Figure-2). This material contains 37.5% hydrogen peroxide, which promotes remarkable whitening procedure with a start to finish time of less than an hour. It is a chemically activated bleach and hence any kind of bleaching light is not used for this process.

Figure 2: Pola Office Plus Bleaching Kit

Oral prophylaxis was performed. Cheek/lip retractor was placed and pre-operative photograph was taken. Teeth were dried, gingival shield VLC (visible light cure) was applied to both upper and lower arches, slightly overlapping enamel and inter proximal spaces. Light-cured in a fanning motion for 20-30 seconds until it is cured. Thus protection and isolation of gingival tissue was achieved (Figure-3).

Figure 3: Application Of Gingival Barrier

Firmly attached nozzle to the pola office syringe. Dispensed small amount of mixing gel on to a mixing pad until uniform gel was extruded. A thick layer of gel was applied to all the labial surfaces of teeth undergoing treatment (figure 4). The gel was left on teeth surfaces for 10 minutes. Suction was performed using a surgical aspirator tip.

Figure 4: Application of Bleaching Gel

Three cycles of 10 minutes were performed in the same appointment to complete the in-office procedure. After the last application, all the applied gel was suctioned, washed with

water. Gingival shield barrier was removed by lifting it from one end. The bleaching procedure was completed. Potassium nitrate toothpaste prescribed. Post treatment instructions were given. The patient was asked to return in 10 days to evaluate the results. Using standard visual examination and confirmation with shade guide, a noticeable shade change has occurred. The postoperative shade was determined and it was A1 (figure 5)

Figure 5: Post-operative Photograph

The patient noticed a marked improvement in teeth color and was very pleased with the final outcome. The patient was recalled after 3 months for follow-up.

Case Report

Case 2: A 35 years old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics Chandra Dental College with the chief complaint of discoloration of teeth. During the oral examination of the patient, the key clinical guidelines that are focused on are no or minimal gingival recession, good periodontal health, and the absence of caries. In addition, questions about any history of tooth sensitivity were asked. In the case of this patient he had no history of any kind of sensitivity. The patient's initial shade was an A3 (Figure 6). For this patient, Opalescence boost from ultradent was used (Figure 7). This material contains 40% hydrogen peroxide. It is a chemically activated bleach and hence any kind of bleaching light is not used for this process.

Figure 6: Pre-operative Photograph

Figure 7:Opalescence Boost

Oral prophylaxis was performed. Teeth were dried. Gingival barrier was applied along the gingival margins overlapping approximately 0.5 mm onto the enamel and light-cured for 20 seconds .(Figure 8).

Figure 8:Placement of gingival barrier

Bleach is mixed just prior to its application .Two plungers get attached to one another. We pushed the clear syringe plunger to rupture the membrane inside and then pushed the red plunger to transfer its content into the clear syringe. In this way bleach combines with activator. Continuous pushing of the two plungers were done alternatively to ensure proper mixing. Process was repeated to around 35-40 times .The gel was emptied in the red syringe before it was separated from clear syringe. Delivery tip was attached on to the red syringe and its even flow was verified on the piece of gauge . A thick layer of gel was then applied to the labial surfaces of teeth in layers approximately 1mm thick (Figure 9). The gel was left on teeth surfaces for 20 minutes. After 20 minutes , bleach was removed with suction only.

Figure 9:Application of gel

Two cycles of 20 minutes were performed in the same

appointment. After the application, all the applied gel was suctioned. Teeth were rinsed with water and suction was done simultaneously . The bleaching procedure was completed. Potassium nitrate paste was prescribed. Post treatment instructions were given. The patient was asked to return in 10 days to evaluate the results. Using standard visual examination and confirmation with shade guide , a noticeable shade change had occurred. The postoperative shade was then A1 (Figure-10). The patient was recalled after 3 months for follow-up .

Figure 10: Post – operative photograph

Discussion

Tooth bleaching is one of the most common and economic methods to treat the discoloration of teeth. Dental aesthetics, especially tooth color, is of great importance for the majority of people and teeth discoloration can also negatively influence the quality of life especially from a social point of view^{8,9}. So various tooth bleaching procedures have come into practice¹⁰. However, bleaching involves risks that include increased tooth sensitivity and mild gingival irritation¹¹. While performing in-office bleaching, both proper isolation and protection of mucosal tissues are essential¹². Sensitivity during whitening of vital teeth is associated to high concentrations of peroxide and exposure time to dental structures, and this sensitivity during bleaching is typically moderate and can be easily controlled^{12,13}. Excessive bleaching procedure should be avoided as hydrogen peroxide can make the enamel surface rough. The decomposition of hydrogen peroxide material will interact with the organic components of teeth resulting in organic loss making enamel surface rough. Also it can partially remove protein pellicle over the enamel crystals exposing the crystal surface thereby causing mild sensitivity. Dentists may also wish to consider prescribing NSAIDs prior to treatment since post-treatment sensitivity is unpredictable¹⁴. In case of sensitivity, potassium nitrate pastes (5%), NaF (2%), calcium based desensitizing pastes are prescribed¹⁵. The potassium ions that are most likely to be the active component works by lowering the sensitivity activity of the dentine by the depolarization action of potassium¹⁶. Whereas fluorides occludes the dentinal tubules which are exposed or reduces the flow of dental lymph towards the pulp, effectively halting the transmission of stimuli. Multiple appointments are typically scheduled one week apart to allow sensitivity to abate. A “bleaching light” sometimes used with in-office bleaching procedures as well. Some reports suggest that pulpal temperature can increase with bleaching light use, depending on the light source and exposure time. Some study suggests that use of some lights may result in light radiation exposure levels approaching or exceeding safety limits^{16,17}. Pulpal irritation and tooth sensitivity may be higher with the use of bleaching lights or heat application, and caution has been advised with their use. Therefore , in both the above cases, light activation was not done due to no proven benefits .In both the bleaching procedures , sensitivity produced was insignificant¹⁷. The only difference was in the number of applications required to

obtain desired result. Due to dehydration, which reverses with time. The actual color change will not be evident until 2 to 6 weeks after bleaching treatment.

Conclusion

Vital tooth bleaching is an efficient treatment procedure that can appreciably change the appearance of teeth. Patient satisfaction has been demonstrated after the use of professionally dispensed bleaching treatment. Based on the clinical results reported with professional vital tooth bleaching, it is a viable, aesthetic treatment for the discolored dentition. In today's world of immediate gratification, in-office bleaching is one of the most requested procedures in many dental offices. Bleaching using both the 37.5% hydrogen peroxide and 40% hydrogen peroxide, are secure options for bleaching vital teeth maintaining the substrate healthy.

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